

Action of lithium ethylenediamine on 1,4-diketone

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Abstract : Reactions of lithium ethylenediamine (Li/EDA) have been carried out on 1,4-diketones such as cholest-4(5)-en-3,6-dione (1) and hexane-2,5-dione (7). The resulting compounds have been characterized by optical rotation, IR, mass spectra and by comparison with authentic samples.

Keywords : 1,4-Diketone, lithium ethylenediamine.

Introduction

Reactions of Li/EDA on compounds bearing various functional groups have been reported earlier by our group¹⁻⁴. Action of the said reagent on 1,2-diketones yielded a novel method for the one pot synthesis of pyrazine derivative⁵. Reaction of this reagent 1,3-diketone compounds has also been reported⁶. Encouraged by these findings we have extended the reaction on two representative 1,4-diketones, e.g. cholest-4(5)-en-3,6-dione (1) and hexane-2,5-dione (7) and the results are described in the present paper.

Results and discussion

Cholest-4(5)-en-3,6-dione (1) prepared by Jones' oxidation of cholesterol on treatment with Li/EDA in the usual manner¹ afforded two compounds, (A) and (B). The compounds were separated by column chromatography. The first compound (A) eluted by petroleum ether was purified by repeated crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture. It was analysed for $C_{27}H_{48}$, m.p. 81–82 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 27.9^\circ$. It did not respond to TNM test for unsaturation. The IR spectrum of the compound (A) did not show any absorption for carbonyl group. In its mass spectrum, compound (A) showed molecular ion peak at m/z 372. Finally by comparison with an authentic sample (mixed m.p., co-IR, co-TLC) the compound was identified as cholestane (4) (lit.⁷ m.p. 80–83 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 28.7^\circ$).

The more polar fraction of the reaction product (B) eluted by toluene was also purified by repeated crystallization from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH mixture. Analysis showed its

molecular formula to be $C_{27}H_{48}O$, m.p. 140–141 °C and $[\alpha]_D + 24^\circ$. It did not respond to TNM test for unsaturation. However, the IR spectrum of the compound (B) showed peaks at 3400 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl group. On the basis of above and by a comparison (mixed m.p., co-IR, co-TLC) with an authentic sample, compound (B) was identified as cholestan-3 β -ol⁸. The structure of compound (B) was further established to be the alcohol (5) by preparation of its acetate derivative (Py-Ac₂O) which was found to be identical with an authentic sample of cholestan-3 β -yl acetate⁸, (6) $C_{29}H_{50}O_2$, m.p. 110–111 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 10^\circ$.

Reaction of hexane-2,5-dione (7) in the similar fashion also yielded two compounds (C) and (D). The compounds were separated by column chromatography. The first compound (C) eluted by petroleum ether was purified by double distillation. It was analysed for C_6H_{14} , b.p. 68 °C. It did not respond to TNM test for unsaturation. The IR spectrum of the compound (C) did not show any absorption for carbonyl group. In its mass spectrum the compound (C) showed molecular ion peak at m/z 86. Finally by comparison with an authentic sample (co-IR, co-TLC) the compound was identified as *n*-hexane, (8) (lit.⁹ b.p. 69 °C). The more polar fraction of the reaction product (D) eluted by toluene is also purified by double distillation. Analysis showed its molecular formula to be $C_6H_{14}O_2$, b.p. 218 °C and $[\alpha]_D - 17.6^\circ$. It did not respond to TNM test for unsaturation. However, the IR spectrum of the compound (B) showed a peak at 3400 cm^{-1} for hydroxyl group. On the basis of above and by a comparison (co-IR, co-TLC) with an authentic sample compound (D) was identified as hexane-2,5-diol⁹ (9).

Discussion of reaction mechanism :

Contrary to the 1,2- and 1,3-diketo compounds, in this particular case the reduction takes place in the simplest way. In case of cholest-4(5)-en-3,6-dione (1) the deoxygenation at 6-position probably takes place by reduction of the diketone (1) to (2) followed by scission of the C–O bond⁴ to give the C–H bond (3). Further reduction of (3) yields (4) and (5) as observed in the earlier cases¹⁰.

However, with the saturated diketone (7), the reduction takes place in stepwise manner and yields the corresponding diol (9) and the corresponding hydrocarbon (8) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) was used during the investigations. IR spectra were recorded in nujol on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. UV spectra were recorded in methanol on Shimadzu-UV 240 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on Varian Mat 711 (70 eV) and JMS-D 300 (70 eV) by EI/CI method. All the rotations were taken in CHCl₃ solution. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60–120 mesh, BDH). TLC was performed on chromatoplate of silica gel G (Glaxo and BDH) and the spots were located by exposing to iodine chamber.

Jones' oxidation of cholesterol : Preparation of cholest-4(5)-en-2,6-dione (1) :

To a solution of cholesterol (1 g) in pure acetone (150 ml) Jones' reagent was added dropwise with shaking until a faint orange colour persisted. The mixture was kept for 1 h, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and then ether was evaporated out.

The residue dissolved in minimum volume of toluene was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g). The chromatogram was developed in petroleum ether and eluted with pet. ether and pet. ether-toluene (4 : 1). The fractions eluted with pet. ether-toluene of same R_f value were combined (0.8 g) and purified by repeated crystallization from CHCl₃-MeOH mixture to afford white crystals, m.p. 121– 122 °C, m.f. C₂₇H₄₂O₂, IR : ν_{max} (nujol) 1690 cm⁻¹ (α,β unsaturated ketone), UV (250 nm, ε 11000) and was identified as cholest-4(5)-en-2,6-dione (1) by a comparison with authentic specimen (lit.¹¹ m.p. 123 °C, UV 252 nm¹²).

Treatment of cholest-4(5)-en-2,6-dione (1) with Li/EDA :

The detailed experimental procedure is already reported⁶. The product obtained after usual work up was separated by column chromatography and purified by repeated crystallization from CHCl₃-MeOH mixture. The

less polar fraction eluted with pet. ether (0.3 g) showed m.p. 81–83 °C, m.f. $C_{27}H_{48}$, $[\alpha]_D + 27.9^\circ$ (lit.⁷ m.p. 80–83 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 26.7^\circ$) was identified as cholestane (4) (Found : C, 87.02; H, 12.87. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{48}$: C, 87.10; H, 12.90%).

The polar fraction eluted with pet. ether-toluene (1 : 4) (0.35 g) showed m.p. 140–141 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 24^\circ$, IR : 3400 cm^{-1} , m.f. $C_{27}H_{47}OH$, and was identified as cholestane-3 β -ol (5) by comparison (m.p., co-IR, co-TLC) with an authentic sample (lit.⁸ m.p. 142 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 24^\circ$) (Found : C, 83.10; H, 12.50. Calcd. for $C_{27}H_{48}O$: C, 83.40; H, 12.50%).

Preparation of cholestan-3 β -yl acetate :

Compound (0.1 g) was treated with acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (2 ml) and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and then poured into ice cold water and worked up in the usual manner. The solid obtained after usual work up was crystallized from a mixture of chloroform-methanol to afford crystals of acetate, m.p. 110–111 °C, $[\alpha]_D + 10^\circ$ which was found to be identical (mixed m.p., co-IR and co-TLC) with an authentic specimen of cholestan-3 β -yl acetate⁸ (Found : C, 80.78; H, 11.50. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{50}O_2$: C, 80.93; H, 11.62%).

Treatment of hexane-2,5-dione (7) with Li/EDA :

The product obtained after usual work up was separated by column chromatography and purified by double distillation. The less polar fraction eluted with pet. ether (0.2 g) showed b.p. 68 °C, m.f. C_6H_{14} , (lit.⁹ b.p. 69 °C) was identified as *n*-hexane (8) (Found : C, 83.70; H, 16.30. Calcd. for C_6H_{14} : C, 83.72; H, 16.30%).

The polar fraction eluted with toluene (1 : 4) (0.15 g) showed b.p. 218 °C, $[\alpha]_D - 17.6^\circ$, IR : 3400 cm^{-1} , m.f. $C_6H_{14}O_2$, was identified as hexane-2,5-diol (9) (Found : C, 72.78; H, 11.90. Calcd. for $C_6H_{14}O_2$: C, 72.88; H, 11.86%).

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